
A Human-Centered XAI System for Phishing Detection

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Abstract

AI models are widely used in cybersecurity to identify digital content that could be malicious. This is also the case with phishing emails: when a defense system detects a suspicious message, users are typically presented with warning dialogs that inform them of the risks. However, warnings are often designed without adequate consideration of the end user, leading to incorrect decisions that lower the benefit of the AI models. To overcome the limitations identified in the literature, this paper presents an XAI phishing detection system built following a human-centered design approach. It classifies phishing emails and generates polymorphic warning dialogs that explain to the user why the email might be a scam, with the ultimate goal

of supporting a more informed decision on whether or not to open suspicious content.

Author Keywords

Phishing; Explainable Artificial Intelligence.

CSS Concepts

• **Security and privacy ~ Human and societal aspects of security and privacy**; *Usability in security and privacy*;

Introduction

Nowadays, phishing is one of the biggest cyber threats, affecting thousands of users each day [3]. To contrast this attack many methods are employed for the detection of dangerous content, but the most effective ones are based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) [1, 14]. AI models can detect phishing emails and websites very precisely, but they still cannot replace humans. Indeed, automatizing the phishing detection task would inevitably lead to, e.g., blocking or deleting important emails, potentially compromising the user's productivity. Therefore, users must make the final decision about accessing the content. This is typically done by alerting the user about the dangerous nature of an email by showing them warning dialogs. However, human factors like stress, fear, habituation, and hurry can lead users to bypass warnings [8]. Moreover, users can lack the expertise or time to analyze the malicious

content on their own. All these factors contribute to increasing the number of users that fall victim to phishing attacks.

This position paper presents an XAI system for email phishing detection. It consists of an XAI model that classifies phishing emails and a warning dialog that alerts the users about a potential scam and explains why the email might be dangerous. Both these components have been designed following a human-centered approach. The XAI model takes into account human factors in phishing attacks [8], in particular, *habituation* to warning dialogs, which reduces the effectiveness of warnings [15]. To this aim, the model has been trained not only considering the classification accuracy but also its ability to produce multiple explanations, an aspect that prevents users from becoming accustomed to warning messages [9]. The warning dialog proposed in our solution implements an active behavior [9], i.e., it interrupts users and forces them to notice the warning. The warning dialog also contains an explanation message designed to help lay users detect phishing emails easily. Overall, this system aims to improve the effectiveness of warning dialogs and protect users from phishing attacks.

Limitations of the existing warning dialogs

To increase the effectiveness of the warning dialogs that alert users in case of phishing attacks, it is essential to consider design guidelines and lessons from the literature (e.g., [4, 7, 9, 20, 23, 26]). For example, a key issue that affects user motivation to heed warnings is the lack of explanation in warning messages [4]. Users need proper explanations to understand the rationale behind warnings and the danger posed by, for example, a phishing email. Using

explanation messages, the system can increase motivation and trust [24], facilitating understanding and ultimately improving the effectiveness of warning dialogs against phishing attacks [4, 6]. Another issue is the *habituation effect*, where users become accustomed to seeing the same warning and are more likely to ignore it [15]. Polymorphic warnings can help limit this effect by changing their appearance and content to prevent user habituation [2]. Overall, designing warning dialogs that consider these factors can improve the effectiveness of email phishing detection systems.

An XAI system for email phishing detection

To address the aforementioned problems in the context of phishing emails, we propose an XAI system able to generate warnings that i) explain why an email is considered suspicious, and ii) change their content depending on the specific phishing cues in the email. In the following, we briefly describe how we designed the two main components of the proposed system, i.e., the XAI model and the warning dialogs.

Designing the XAI model

The majority of current phishing detection systems rely on non-transparent AI models [1, 14], also known as black-box models [12], which can be difficult to interpret. To address this issue, explainable AI (XAI) techniques can be used to generate explanations of a model's decision-making process [17, 19, 21], although these explanations are typically understandable by AI experts. The existing approaches involve retrieving a feature importance vector, which describes the contribution of each feature to the classification outcome, in order to identify the most influential features in classifying an email as phishing. The most important feature can then be used to create an

explanation in the warning dialog. In the following, we briefly report how we selected the features to be explained and how we trained the XAI model.

CHOOSING THE FEATURES AND THE MODEL

The first aspect to consider in designing the XAI model relates to the set of features to train it on. They represent the starting point of the explanation to be provided to the users. To this aim, the features of the model must be related to concepts that are not too technical, as they are intended to be quickly understood by lay users as well. For example, we cannot expect a lay user to understand what a DNS server is in a short amount of time; therefore, any feature that is related to this concept (e.g., the absence of a DNS record for the domain site linked in the email) should not be included in the set of features for the model. Even though we reduced the feature set to a considerably smaller subset, we empirically showed that it is still possible to obtain solid performance [11]. From an analysis of the literature, we identified all the features used to train phishing detection algorithms. The resulting set, containing 140 features, has been reduced by filtering in only those features related to concepts easily explainable to the users. Also, features that were too expensive to compute in real time, were discarded. This process was conducted by a panel of 4 HCI experts based on their knowledge and common sense.

The datasets used to train the model (*SpamAssassin* [22] and *Enron* corpus [16]) was reduced to these 18 features. The final datasets have been used to train different models among the ones that are typically used for this task and that are suitable for the explanation, i.e., decision tree, logistic regression, random forest,

SVM, multi-layer perceptron (MLP), deep neural network (DNN), and Explainable Boosting Machine [19]. To retrieve the explanations from the black-box models (i.e., random forest, SVM, MLP, and DNN) we applied two different post-hoc XAI techniques: LIME [21] and SHAP [17].

CONSIDERING USER HABITUATION IN TRAINING THE MODELS

Another aspect to consider in training the model regards the diversity of the most influential features according to the feature importance vector. In other words, we should disregard the XAI models which frequently have few very predominant features and a lot of features that are rarely considered. To measure this aspect, we introduced a new metric called *h-score* (i.e., "heterogeneity score"), defined following this procedure:

1. compute the feature importance on every instance of the dataset;
2. consider the top S most important features from the feature importance vector (e.g., we set S=3),
3. count how many times each feature appears among the top S features - the x array will contain the count for each feature,
4. compute the h-score on the x array which is defined as follows:

$$\text{h-score}(x) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n f^2(x_i - \bar{x}),$$

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} (1 - \alpha)x, & x > 0 \\ \alpha x, & x \leq 0 \end{cases}, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1$$

where n is the number of features, \bar{x} is the mean value over the x array, and α is used to arbitrarily weigh the cases in which a feature's frequency is either higher or

Metrics to design explanation messages

Flesch-Kincaid grade

level: this metric is used to measure the readability level of the text. It ranges between 0 and 18 (lower is better) and estimates the reading grade level of a text according to the US education system [10].

Smog Index: this metric measures the level of understandability of a text. It assesses the approximate number of years of education required to fully understand a text (lower is better) [18].

Sentiment score: this score indicates the perceived connotation of a text. It is a value that ranges between 1 (positive connotation) and -1 (negative connotation). We want warning messages to be perceived as negative as possible, as they should incite negative emotions in the user [13].

lower than the average. An h-score equal to zero indicates that the features are all equally important, while a very high score indicates that one or few features dominate over the others. In this way, we can compare different XAI models by considering not only the typical metrics such as precision and recall but also the *h-score*.

Designing the warning dialogs

The warning dialog appears when a user tries to open a phishing email, preventing them from accessing the email content [6] (Figure 1). It blocks the user's interaction and forces their attention to the message [5, 9]. In the bottom part of the dialog, there are two buttons: to prevent the user from accidentally ignoring the warning, the default choice relies on the "Back to Safety" button (bottom-right), which makes the user safely return to the email client; if the user really wanted to proceed, they would have to first click on the "Show details" button (bottom-left), and only then click on the link ("Click here") to access the suspicious email. The design process followed well-established guidelines and lessons from the literature (e.g., [4, 7, 9, 20, 23, 26]).

The core of the warning is represented by the explanation message. For each of the 18 features used to train the XAI model, 2 messages have been manually generated considering three metrics: the readability score, measured by Flesch-Kincaid grade level [10]; the understandability score, measured by Smog Index [18]; and the sentiment score [13]. Each explanation message follows a consistent layout [25] and includes: i) *the description of the phishing feature* (in Figure 1: "In the URL ... the top-level domain (e.g., ".com") is in an abnormal position"), ii) *the*

explanation of the hazard ("This could indicate that the URL leads to a fake website), and iii) *the consequences of a successful attack* ("Such websites might steal your personal information"). When an email is classified as phishing by the XAI model, the system considers the 3 most influential features according to the feature importance vector and randomly chooses one to build the explanation message. Then, one of the two messages created for the selected feature is randomly selected and included in the warning dialog.

Figure 1: Example of warning dialog with an explanation.

A user study

We recently conducted a user study to evaluate the performance of the proposed solutions. In this section we report a summary of the main aspects of this study, all the details can be found in [6].

The study aimed to understand if *preventing the user from accessing the email content improves their susceptibility to phishing attacks*. A between-subject design has been adopted. The between-subject levels are the warning presented in the previous Section,

another one similar to the first one but without any explanation, and a baseline [20].

The study has been performed online through the Prolific platform. A total of 300 participants were recruited and randomly assigned to the three experimental conditions. Each participant was asked to interact with an email client by reading all the emails in the inbox and checking that the links in them, if any, are working. By clicking on a legitimate email participants could access the email content. In the case of phishing emails, the warning corresponding to the experimental condition was shown.

According to the results related to the click-through rate, the warnings with explanations are more effective in protecting users from phishing emails compared to the warnings without explanations and the state-of-the-art ones. Furthermore, the use of explanations was found to be helpful in preventing users from mistakenly ignoring legitimate emails that were incorrectly flagged due to possible email misclassification.

Conclusions

This position paper reports an XAI system that defends users from phishing attacks. At the workshop, the authors of this paper will present the technical details of the trained model, as well as more details on the experimental study. As future work, we are planning a longitudinal study in a company to understand if the habituation effect is lowered thanks to the polymorphic behavior.

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